

Response to Request for Comment on Draft Desirable Characteristics of Repositories for Managing and Sharing Data Resulting from Federally Funded or Supported Research.

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The UK Data Archive is a discipline-specific (social sciences) data archive which has been in continuous existence since 1967. The UK Data Service is an ESRC-funded service which is led from the UK Data Archive at the University of Essex, and works in partnership with other UK institutions.

<https://www.federalregister.gov/documents/2020/01/17/2020-00689/request-for-public-comment-on-draft-desirable-characteristics-of-repositories-for-managing-and-sharing-data-resulting-from-federally-funded-or-supported-research>

Desirable Characteristics of Repositories for Managing and Sharing Data Resulting From Federally Funded or Supported Research

I. Desirable Characteristics for All Data Repositories

A. Persistent Unique Identifiers: Assigns datasets a citable, persistent unique identifier (PUIID), such as a digital object identifier (DOI) or accession number, to support data discovery, reporting (e.g., of research progress), and research assessment (e.g., identifying the outputs of Federally funded research). The PUIID points to a persistent landing page that remains accessible even if the dataset is de-accessioned or no longer available.

We note that an accession number is not necessarily semantically identical to a PUIID. We would suggest that both are necessary. (It is not impossible for a PUIID to include the repository accession number. In the example below, SN (representing Study Number) is the accession number, and that number is clearly identifiable in the full doi.)

Office for National Statistics, University of Manchester, Cathie Marsh Institute for Social Research (CMIST), UK Data Service. (2019). *Quarterly Labour Force Survey, July - September 2018: Teaching Dataset*. [data collection]. Office for National Statistics, [original data producer(s)]. Office for National Statistics. SN: 8499, <http://doi.org/10.5255/UKDA-SN-8499-1>

B. Long-term sustainability: Has a long-term plan for managing data, including guaranteeing long-term integrity, authenticity, and availability of datasets; building on a stable technical infrastructure and funding plans; has contingency plans to ensure data are available and maintained during and after unforeseen events.

Long-term should include a minimum number of guaranteed years and a mechanism and terms for appraisal over time. Any significant time period where user or technical change may imply a need to change the data or metadata implies a need for active preservation (beyond the bit-level).

Availability does not imply usability. A dataset may be available for reuse in fifty years, but by being stored on punched cards does not allow them to be used by anyone without a punched card reader!

C. Metadata: Ensures datasets are accompanied by metadata sufficient to enable discovery, reuse, and citation of datasets, using a schema that is standard to the community the repository serves.

The digital preservation community tends to use the phrase “independently understandable”. The implication is that a user can discover, access and use the content without additional help from the repository. This places a high overhead on “general repositories” which need to assume a general

user base. Discipline-specific repositories need only make assumptions about the knowledge within their discipline in the long-term.

D. Curation & Quality Assurance: Provides, or has a mechanism for others to provide, expert curation and quality assurance to improve the accuracy and integrity of datasets and metadata.

There is a general discussion in the community around quality measures. Our opinion is that the repository should be responsible for the integrity of datasets and metadata, but the original producer needs to be responsible for its quality. Within the social sciences community we often use the “pregnant men” scenario to describe basic checking. If a dataset includes inconsistencies such as pregnant men, we return the data to the data owners and they are expected to recode or correct these inconsistencies. We also provide a check on the level of anonymisation. On occasion a data depositor has included personally identifiable information in a dataset which was expected to be openly accessible. Errors like this are highlighted to the data owner before data is prepared for long-term preservation.

This provision is helpful, but needs clearer pointers to the responsibilities of the repository and the data creator/owner.

E. Access: Provides broad, equitable, and maximally open access to datasets, as appropriate, consistent with legal and ethical limits required to maintain privacy and confidentiality.

Methods of accessing data should not drive the access level. The access level (based on the content of the data) should drive the method of accessing data.

F. Free & Easy to Access and Reuse: Makes datasets and their metadata accessible free of charge in a timely manner after submission and with broadest possible terms of reuse or documented as being in the public domain.

This statement has some overlap with the previous one. The phrase “documented as being in the public domain” is unlikely to be a consideration for more recent works. Copyright should always be clarified before a repository accepts data, otherwise worldwide copyright laws may be being broken. Note also that copyright is not rescinded on the basis of a CC license.

G. Reuse: Enables tracking of data reuse (e.g., through assignment of adequate metadata and PUID).

This is a knotty problem. The enablement of tracking does not imply that tracking can take place. There is considerable evidence across the globe that data users are not as careful about referencing/citing data as they might be. The responsibility for ensuring that tracking can take place must lie within the hands of the user and not the repository. For example, the UK Data Service can track some use of data which we hold on behalf of others, but this is likely to be a small proportion of the use which actually takes place. In reality a repository will only be able to “Provide the means for the tracking of data reuse through the assignment of adequate metadata and persistent identifiers (PUIDs)” --- which may be more appropriate wording for this characteristic.

H. Secure: Provides documentation of meeting accepted criteria for security to prevent unauthorized access or release of data, such as the criteria described in the International Standards Organization's ISO 27001 (<https://www.iso.org/isoiec-27001-information-security.html>) or the National Institute of Standards and Technology's 800-53 controls (<https://nvd.nist.gov/800-53>).

International standards like ISO 27001 are a high bar for some repositories. Question: providing documentation to whom? If this is publicly available it might increase the risk of someone attacking the repository. If this is not publicly available it may in effect be of no value.

I. Privacy: Provides documentation that administrative, technical, and physical safeguards are employed in compliance with applicable privacy, risk management, and continuous monitoring requirements.

We would change the word privacy to confidentiality here. The risks to privacy per se should be built into the data collection process; the risks to confidentiality are bound up with the management of the data.

J. Common Format: Allows datasets and metadata to be downloaded, accessed, or exported from the repository in a standards-compliant, and preferably non-proprietary, format.

We have yet to identify mechanisms such as community-based standards registries to identify appropriate formats. While we would agree that these data (and metadata) should be made available in non-proprietary formats, this should not preclude making them available in proprietary formats if the community desires that.

K. Provenance: Maintains a detailed logfile of changes to datasets and metadata, including date and user, beginning with creation/upload of the dataset, to ensure data integrity.

Both pre-deposit provenance and post-deposit provenance should potentially be included here. Pre-deposit provenance also provides a mechanism for managing rights information.

II. Additional Considerations for Repositories Storing Human Data (Even if De-Identified)

A. Fidelity to Consent: Restricts dataset access to appropriate uses consistent with original consent (such as for use only within the context of research on a specific disease or condition).

As an addition to the statement above, it should be clear that it is the responsibility of the data creator to ensure that the consent (of the original data collection) was carried out in compliance with local ethical/institutional review board.

B. Restricted Use Compliant: Enforces submitters' data use restrictions, such as preventing reidentification or redistribution to unauthorized users.

This is a perfectly reasonable statement, however there may be times when data submitters need a more "generalist" approach to understanding their restrictions. Often times, data submitters are more risk adverse than they need to be. Data repositories should not make the decisions on behalf of the data submitters, but they may need to provide guidance so that the data submitters' restrictions are appropriate.

C. Privacy: Implements and provides documentation of security techniques appropriate for human subjects' data to protect from inappropriate access.

To make this a more overarching criteria, the words "for human subjects" could be replaced with "the". (i.e., : Implements and provides documentation of security techniques appropriate for the data to protect from inappropriate access.") Some data may need restricted access and protection for other reasons than just protection of human subjects --- sensitive commercial information, rights management, the protection of culturally or ecologically sensitive information such as the locations of artefacts or species. So this statement may need to be broader than just human subjects.

D. Plan for Breach: Has security measures that include a data breach response plan.

Agreed

E. Download Control: Controls and audits access to and download of datasets.

Agreed – and not necessarily just for human subject data.

F. Clear Use Guidance: Provides accompanying documentation describing restrictions on dataset access and use.

Again, this should not just be for confidential data. Data which has been anonymised will, for example, have a (very small) risk of disclosure. Making it clear that the user must not attempt to identify individuals is part of our licence regime.

G. Retention Guidelines: Provides documentation on its guidelines for data retention.

This may be a language issue but retention may apply to both the length of time that a dataset is expected to be maintained or whether or not there are requests for the withdrawal of personal information in a dataset.

H. Violations: Has plans for addressing violations of terms-of-use by users and data mismanagement by the repository.

It might be better to use the word processes as opposed to plans. Having plans might imply that these are only in the development phase and not operational.

I. Request Review: Has an established data access review or oversight group responsible for reviewing data use requests.

In the UK all accesses to data which is deemed personal under the Data Protection Act (or any other legal gateway) are approved by Data Access Committees which have different processes for reviewing data use requests.

Conclusion

In general these characteristics are all sensible and valid; in our opinion only some wording changes for clarity or extensions to provide additional meaningful detail are necessary. It is also worth noting that the [CoreTrustSeal](#) is a community-based standard which provides an assessment against trustworthy digital repositories. They already provide detailed guidance on a set of actions/activities which are required for a digital repository to be considered to be trustworthy. So, their requirements overlap with and complement the characteristics here. However, there is little here which is not already within the CoreTrustSeal, and it might be worth considering making the first characteristic to be certified against the CoreTrustSeal.

Two significant omissions from this set of characteristics are noticeable. The first covers **Scope** --- the repositories should have a detailed scope of engagement. This is important because it allows a relationship between the mission (defining scope) and the ability to deal appropriately with the data. Scope also allows for clarity in the skills which are required to manage a repository – and having the correct skills to carry out the activities which are required by these characteristics.

The second covers **user support**. Some user support is generalist, but some is specific. All repositories which are dealing with specialist data, should be in a position to provide some human-level support about the data. (Not just the finding and accessing of data.) Therefore I would also

recommend these two additional characteristics. Repositories may have additional objectives which are not specifically required, but help facilitate the process. The UK Data Service, for example, carries out a fair amount of **training**, which is specific to the data which it facilitates access to. This is not a requirement, of course, but it allows for better (a higher quality) level of support to researchers.

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